

ISLAMIC FINTECH AND SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This study is based on a systematic literature review, adopting a qualitative approach, to measure the scientific contribution to topics linking Islamic Fintech and sustainable development. The analysis focused on journal publications indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, in line with PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. Using the R package's Biblioshiny tool for interactive data mining, we selected 30 articles published between 2019 and 2023, paying particular attention to their quality and relevance. The results highlight the central role of Islamic Fintech in promoting sustainable development, notably in terms of economic growth, reducing inequality and responsible consumption. However, a number of challenges remain, mainly related to regulation and technology adoption, especially in contexts such as Morocco. The study also highlights the need for further research into the integration of advanced technologies to optimize the impact of Islamic Fintech solutions.

Key-words : Fintech ; Islamic Fintech ; Sustainable development ; Financial inclusion ; SLR

المخلص

تستند هذه الدراسة إلى مراجعة منهجية للأدبيات التي اعتمدت نهجاً نوعياً لقياس الإسهام العلمي في الموضوعات التي تربط بين التكنولوجيا المالية الإسلامية والتنمية المستدامة. وقد ركز التحليل على منشورات المجالات المفهرسة في موقعي Scopus و Web of Science، بما يتماشى مع إرشادات PRISMA (عناصر الإبلاغ المفضلة للمراجعات المنهجية والتحليلات الوصفية). وباستخدام أداة "ببليوشيني" (Biblioshiny) الخاصة بحزمة R للتعقيب التفاعلي عن البيانات، اخترنا 30 مقالة نُشرت بين عامي 2019 و 2023، مع إيلاء اهتمام خاص لجودتها وأهميتها. تسلط النتائج الضوء على الدور المحوري للتكنولوجيا المالية الإسلامية في تعزيز التنمية المستدامة، لا سيما فيما يتعلق بالنمو الاقتصادي والحد من عدم المساواة والاستهلاك المسؤول. ومع ذلك، لا يزال هناك عدد من التحديات التي لا تزال قائمة، والتي تتعلق بشكل رئيسي بالتنظيم واعتماد التكنولوجيا، لا سيما في سياقات مثل المغرب. كما تسلط الدراسة الضوء على الحاجة إلى مزيد من البحث في دمج التقنيات المتقدمة لتحسين تأثير حلول التكنولوجيا المالية الإسلامية.

الكلمات المفتاحية : التكنولوجيا المالية؛ التكنولوجيا المالية الإسلامية؛ التنمية المستدامة؛ الشمول المالي؛ SLR

1. INTRODUCTION

In the midst of economic chaos Islamic finance, underpinned by its fundamental principles of ethics and societal commitment, is clearly well placed to contribute effectively to the promotion of sustainable development, one of the key concerns of our time. It's an era marked by the availability of advanced technologies, offering the infrastructure and data needed to develop more sophisticated financial solutions, complemented by financial technology to enable them to operate more efficiently and inclusively. It can amplify this reach by facilitating access to financial services for marginalized populations, notably by financing green projects and promoting transparency and accountability in financial transactions.

Fintech has emerged as one of the most disruptive technologies of the 21st century, is a phenomenon, a disruption and an opportunity for Islamic finance to show its full potential and offer the world a truly sustainable, ethical and alternative financial system. It is also based on sustainability principles and can offer many benefits to Islamic financial institutions, provided that regulators safeguard financial integrity, consumer data security and financial inclusion (Hassan, Zulfikar, et al., 2022). Its use is also in line with Sharia principles, provided it does not contradict them (Dawood et al., 2022).

Indeed, it is able to improve access to financial services and promote financial inclusion, particularly in emerging markets such as Indonesia, as Hudaefi (2020) points out. Combining the strengths of Fintech and Islamic finance can thus enable the emergence of a more equitable and inclusive financial system, meeting the needs of people worldwide and helping to build a more sustainable future.

Moreover, Morocco, which is part of a dynamic economic growth context on the African continent, is becoming a fast-growing Fintech market. Indeed, the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst, accelerating the adoption of digital and contactless payments. This has led to a significant 17% increase in the number of Fintech companies in Africa by 2023¹. The attractiveness of the Moroccan market is attracting interest from investors, reinforcing the country's position as a regional Fintech hub. This dynamic is stimulating the national economy, encouraging transactions and investments, and creating new job opportunities.

Given the advantages offered by Fintech, it is conceivable that Islamic finance could expand into areas previously inaccessible to traditional banking services (Oseni & Ali, 2019). The initial aim of this expansion is to meet the needs of the community, in compliance with Islamic rules and regulations. As Todorof (2018) reminds us, these rules - the fundamental principles of Sharia law - generally accepted by Muslims, are based on the primacy of group interests over individual interests, i.e. collective benefits take precedence over individual interests (Nik Azman et al., 2020).

As financial institutions continue to look for ways to cut costs, improve efficiency and offer customers a more convenient and transparent banking experience, Fintech is opening up promising prospects. The financial sector can thus reap numerous benefits from the adoption of technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Big Data, automation and predictive analytics.

What's more, with the rise of Fintech in Morocco, Islamic financial institutions (IFIs) have an unprecedented opportunity to catch up and position themselves sustainably against the competition. With the industry still in its infancy in the country, IFIs have the same opportunity as their counterparts to integrate

¹ Retrieved November 24, 2023, from <https://www.the-star.co.ke/>

the most innovative technologies from the outset. However, the literature is flourishing in the conventional sector, whereas it is developing more slowly in the Islamic sector.

To this end, this article aims to explore the literature published in the field of Islamic Fintech, with a particular focus on sustainability-related work, in order to understand the current state of the art and guide future research.

Hence, the problematic of this literature review is as follows: **To what extent does the existing scientific literature highlight the role of Islamic Fintech in sustainable development, and what are the main trends and challenges?**

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- Analyze global trends in Islamic Fintech research in relation to its role in sustainable development, identifying key publications, key players and themes explored.
- Highlight the main contributions of the articles studied, examining the issues addressed and the results obtained.
- Provide recommendations to foster the adoption of Islamic Fintech in Morocco, based on international experiences.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The second section explores the fundamental concepts, while the third presents the research methodology, the results obtained and a synthetic discussion of the literature. The fourth section concludes with recommendations for Morocco.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

2.1. Fintech

From an etymological and general point of view, Fintech is a catchword for financial technology, derived from the combination of two complementary fields: financial services and advanced technological solutions. It refers to the application of emerging technologies to improve financial activities and services.

Financial technologies are attracting the attention of regulators worldwide, and the term “Fintech” encompasses new types of financial services enabled by advances in computer technology and associated business strategies, including digital banking, mobile payments, insurance, wealth management, cryptocurrencies and cross-border payments (Taneja et al., 2024; Yap, 2023). They improve accessibility, efficiency and security for consumers and businesses, transforming the financial landscape (Gopal et al., 2023).

Fintech is characterized by its innovative business models and cutting-edge financial software, redefining the financial industry (Gopal et al., 2023; Taneja et al., 2024), and is recognized for its role in automating and improving the distribution and management of financial services, transforming traditional financial institutions (Kudal et al., 2022; Yap, 2023).

It encompasses diverse technologies, such as blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), big data, the internet of things (IoT), cloud computing, machine learning (ML) and deep learning. As building blocks of Fintech, these technologies support other industry sectors (Liu et al., 2024).

Due to its inherently innovative nature, Fintech implies a constant reassessment of its contours. As a result, the definition of Fintech will probably continue to evolve over time. There is currently no consensus on the definition of Fintech, but academic research has attempted to define it, such as Schueffel (2016) study, which was based on a review of scientific articles and peer-reviewed definitions (Schueffel, 2016; Zavolokina et al., 2016).

Schueffel (2016) conducted an in-depth semantic analysis of the various definitions of Fintech, highlighting a certain diversity of approaches. Although the definitions are many and varied, oscillating between sector, industry and technology, a consensus has emerged around its innovative character and its roots in the financial field. Schueffel (2016) summed up the different perspectives by defining Fintech as “a new financial industry that relies on technology to improve financial activities”.

Puschmann (2017), meanwhile, defines Fintech as “incremental or disruptive innovations in the context of the financial services industry, driven by IT developments resulting in new intra- or inter-organizational business models, products and services, organizations, processes and systems.” (Bouaziz & Sghari, 2021).

The Fintech concept therefore encompasses innovative services, a dynamic business ecosystem and a booming industry. Closely linked, these three dimensions are helping to transform the global financial landscape. It's a movement that is profoundly transforming the financial sector and impacting our daily lives. By combining technology, innovation and a user-centric approach, Fintech is opening up new perspectives for the future of finance.

2.2. Islamic Fintech

Islamic Fintech refers to the application of innovative financial technologies in line with Sharia law. It aims to improve the efficiency of financial services while respecting Islamic ethical values.

Unlike traditional Fintech, which is not subject to specific religious principles, Islamic Fintech ensures that its products and services comply with Sharia prohibitions, such as the ban on interest (riba), excessive speculation (gharar) and investment in sectors that do not conform to Islamic values. It therefore relies on innovative digital business models to offer more inclusive ethical financial services and promote sustainable economic, social, financial and environmental goals, such as poverty reduction and financial inclusion (Oseni & Ali, 2019).

Indeed, Islamic financial products have been modernized by the adoption of Fintech, making them more accessible and affordable thanks to digitization. Consumers, particularly the younger connected generations and digital natives, are particularly interested in this ease of access and are attracted to these Fintech solutions (Dubai Islamic Bank, 2017).

For Islamic financial institutions, Islamic Fintech enables them to reduce operational costs, offer more competitive products and comply with Sharia requirements, as well as facilitating access to modern financial services and improving the transparency and efficiency of financial transactions. However, its development is hampered by regulatory challenges, inadequate governance and uneven adoption of technology. Authorities and stakeholders must work together to remove these obstacles and ensure the steady, sustainable growth of this industry (Alshater et al., 2022).

The main aim of Islamic Fintech is therefore to increase the accessibility, efficiency and affordability of Shariah-compliant financial services, while promoting a fair, equitable and sustainable economic system. It offers investment and financing solutions that respect Islamic laws (Maqasid Al-Shariah), and thus engages in economic practices that benefit society as a whole (Bin Mohamed & Ali, 2019)

As such, Islamic Fintech embodies an alternative model of financial development, combining technology and Islamic ethics to meet the needs of contemporary communities.

2.3. Sustainable development

According to Solow (1992), the sustainability debate has often been dominated by emotions and attitudes rather than formal analysis. To achieve true sustainability, resources need to be evaluated in the light not only of present needs, but also of future needs, in order to treat the interests of future generations fairly (Chichilinisky, 1999).

The Earth Charter (2001) suggests that sustainable development rests on a common ethical basis, guiding the actions of individuals, companies and governments. There is no universally accepted definition, but most definitions of sustainable development deal with the tension between economic growth and environmental protection, with a bias in favor of economic development (Jabareen, 2008).

Sustainable development thus constitutes a global framework designed to meet current needs while guaranteeing the necessary resources for future generations.

It is a vast field of research based on three main interdependent pillars: the economy, the environment and society. It implies equitable economic growth, environmental protection within the limits of current technological and social capacities, and the preservation of human communities and biodiversity. It is also based on the principles of intergenerational equity, social justice and citizen participation (Ukko et al., 2019).

It also revolves around the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) defined by the United Nations (2015) as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which include: no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, access to clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry and innovation, reducing inequality, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, preserving life under water and on land, peace and strong institutions, partnerships for the goals (Wang & Huang, 2021).

These goals stem from earlier initiatives, such as Agenda 21 and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), and have been consolidated by major international agreements, including the Paris Climate Agreement. Implementation of the SDGs is monitored by the UN High-Level Political Forum, and the SDG Division supports their achievement through capacity building, advocacy and international cooperation².

²United Nations, "THE 17 GOALS", Sustainable Development Goals, accessed December 23, 2024, <https://sdgs.un.org/fr/goals>.

Figure 1. 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Source: PNUD, <https://www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals>

The figure above illustrates the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to make people's lives better while protecting the planet. They cover several key areas: eradicating poverty (SDG 1), ensuring food security (SDG 2), securing health and well-being for all (SDG 3) and providing quality education (SDG 4). They are also committed to gender equality (SDG 5), access to water and energy (SDGs 6 and 7), equitable economic growth (SDG 8) and sustainable cities (SDG 11). They promote responsible consumption (SDG 12) and the fight against climate change (SDG 13). Goals 14 and 15 address the preservation of oceans and land, while Goal 16 aims to strengthen peace and justice. Finally, SDG 17 calls for global cooperation to achieve these goals (UNESCO, 2017).

2.4. Financial inclusion

All over the world, whatever the level of development or income, certain segments of the population remain underserved by the formal financial system. Financial inclusion seeks to remedy this situation through easier access to financial products and services offered by banks, microfinance institutions and other formal service providers.

Financial inclusion is the equitable and universal access of individuals and businesses to formal financial services, such as savings, credit, insurance and transfer services. The aim is to reduce dependence on informal mechanisms, which are generally costly and risky, and to improve economic stability. Integrating excluded populations into the financial system reduces inequalities, strengthens economic resilience, stimulates

investment and promotes growth. It also enhances economic opportunities, documents financial transactions and creates a favorable credit history (Shankar, 2013).

According to the United Nations³, financial inclusion refers to access by all households and businesses, at reasonable cost, to a diversified range of financial services such as savings, short- and long-term credit, leasing, factoring, mortgages, insurance, pensions, payments, as well as local and international transfers. This does not mean that every individual is obliged to use all these services, but that everyone should have the opportunity to use them according to their needs. Similarly, the United Nations Capital Development Fund (UNCDF) affirms that financial inclusion is achieved when these services are accessible at an affordable cost, offered by sustainable financial institutions operating within a regulated framework (Chaibou, 2019).

The World Bank defines financial inclusion as the access of individuals and businesses to affordable and useful financial products and services that correspond to their needs (transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance) and that are made available to them in a responsible and sustainable manner. At its most basic level, financial inclusion generally involves holding a bank account with a formal financial institution. This first step enables people to save in total security, and facilitates access to other financial services such as credit, insurance and payments (Fareed, 2020).

3. EMPIRICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

3.1. Methodology deployed

Based on an exhaustive and meticulous search of the Scopus and Web of Science databases, this study offers an assessment of the existing scientific literature on the convergence between Islamic finance and Fintech and its implications for sustainable development. Appropriate keywords and Boolean operators were used to identify articles meeting the inclusion criteria.

Scopus : TITLE-ABS-KEY ("sharia fintec*" OR "islamic fintec*" OR "sharia financial technolog*" OR "islamic financial technolog*") AND ("sustainable development" OR sustainability OR "financial inclusion") AND ("industry 4.0" OR "artificial intelligence" OR blockchain OR "Internet of things").

WoS : "Islamic Fintec*" (Topic) OR "sharia fintec*" (Topic) OR "sharia financial technolog*" (Topic) OR "islamic financial technolog*" (Topic) AND "sustainable development" (Topic) AND "industry 4.0*" (Topic).

A rigorous, multi-stage selection of articles was then carried out to ensure the relevance and reliability of the studies included in this review. Selected articles were subjected to an in-depth thematic analysis to identify key themes, research gaps and implications for practice and future research.

The research method and results of the study are presented in full transparency, in accordance with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines.

³ 2006 United Nations report entitled "Building inclusive financial sectors for development".

Figure 2. Search strategy (Scopus and WoS databases)

Source: Author

This exploration began with an in-depth search of the vast Scopus and Web of Science databases, which enabled us to identify an initial corpus of 106 documents, using predefined keywords and Boolean operators. A rigorous selection process was put in place to guarantee the value and relevance of the results. We applied precise filters to target scientific articles, conference proceedings and book chapters. This was followed by careful manual selection to include documents on the basis of their quality and relevance to the research objectives, and to exclude inappropriate documents and documents written in languages other than English and French, as well as duplicate documents. This process resulted in 30 high-quality documents for analysis and synthesis.

Finally, Zotero and Biblioshiny were used to facilitate the production of results and analyses. These tools provided invaluable support in organizing and visualizing the extracted data.

3.2. Presentation and discussion of results

3.2.1. Results

This study focuses on the characteristics of 30 selected papers, produced by researchers in the field of Islamic Fintech and published in various journals.

The thirty publications include 24 Scopus papers, published between 2020 and 2023 by different authors in several countries. Half of the selected papers (50%, i.e. 12 papers) were published in 2022, with the other years sharing the papers, i.e. 4 for each year. In addition, six relevant documents were extracted from the Web of Science, covering a five-year period from 2019 to 2023. The temporal distribution of publications shows some variability, with no publications in 2021 and a similar distribution (one to two publications) for the other years. Table 1 summarizes our results for publication years.

Table 1. Annual scientific production of selected documents (Scopus / WoS)

Year	Scopus documents	WoS documents
2019	-	1
2020	4	1
2021	4	0
2022	12	2
2023	4	2

Source: Author

Of the Scopus-indexed articles analyzed, "Springer International Publishing" emerged as the leading publisher, contributing 6 book chapters. Notably, 5 of these chapters were part of the book "FinTech in Islamic Financial Institutions: Scope, Challenges, and Implications in Islamic Finance," while the sixth was featured in "Islamic FinTech: Insights and Solutions." Two articles were published each in "Heliyon," "Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity," and "Qualitative Research in Financial Markets (QRFM)." The remaining journals, listed in Table 2, each contributed a single article.

Table 2. Publication journals (Scopus)

Sources	Frequency
Springer international publishing	6
Heliyon	2
Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	2
Qualitative Research in Financial Markets (QRFM)	2
2020 International Conference on Data Analytics for Business and Industry: Way Towards a Sustainable Economy (ICDABI)	1
2022 10th International Conference on Cyber and IT Service Management (CITSM)	1
2022 ASU International Conference in Emerging Technologies for Sustainability and Intelligent Systems (ICETISIS)	1
2023 International Conference on Sustainable Islamic Business and Finance (SIBF)	1
F1000research	1
IGI Global	1

International Journal of Computing and Digital Systems (IJCDS)	1
International Journal of Economics and Business Administration (IJEBA)	1
International Journal of Financial Studies (IJFS)	1
Journal of Islamic Monetary Economics and Finance (JIMF)	1
Journal of Risk and Financial Management (JRFM)	1
Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (JSSH)	1

Source: Author

In addition, the 6 Web of Science articles each come from a separate journal. Table 3 below shows the diversity of sources. This indicates the lack of dominance of any one journal, and the diversity of perspectives presented in research on this topic.

Thus, in addition to the number of publications in each journal, whether in Scopus or WoS, there is a variety in the fields covered by these journals. They cover ICT, economics and business administration, social sciences, finance and Islamic finance.

Table 3. Publication journals (WoS)

Sources	Frequency
3C TIC	1
9th International Economics and Business Management Conference	1
Cuadernos de Economía	1
Etikonomi	1
Journal of Ilahiyat Researches	1
Quality-Access to Success	1

Source: Author

Based on an examination of the documents contained in both databases, Table 4 shows great geographical diversity, with 12 regions represented and also illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. The frequency of publication of three regions in Scopus - Bahrain, Indonesia and Malaysia - is particularly high, with 16, 12 and 9 publications respectively. Next come India and the USA (6 publications each), followed by Jordan (4 publications). The other countries mentioned have a lower scientific output, with 2 or 1 publication. Furthermore, based on the 6 WoS articles, Indonesia clearly dominates with 9 publications, followed by Russia with 3. Brunei and Malaysia each contribute 2 publications.

These results show that Southeast Asia, and Indonesia in particular, occupies a prominent place in the research covered by our articles. These results highlight some fascinating regional trends that merit further exploration. The importance of research in certain regions can be attributed to a number of factors, including the presence of leading research centers, well-targeted funding strategies or strong regional partnerships. The regions represented can reflect the variety of research themes covered by the data set.

The data thus provide a reliable basis for understanding research trends at regional level. However, for a more detailed and in-depth interpretation, further analysis is required, taking into account other indicators.

Table 4. Documents by country (Scopus / WoS)

Scopus		WoS	
Country	Frequency	Country	Frequency
Bahreïn	16	Indonésie	9
Indonésie	12	Russie	3
Malaisie	9	Brunei	2
Inde	6	Malaisie	2
Usa	6		
Jordanie	4		
Oman	2		
Pakistan	2		
Royaume-Uni	2		
Bangladesh	1		

Source: Author

Table 5 below presents an analysis of the most relevant author affiliations, providing interesting information on the most active research institutions in our Scopus database.

We note that the University of Bahrain is a major player, with 10 publications, or almost half of the corpus. This suggests that it plays a key role in the research carried out in these publications. Other institutions, such as the University of New Orleans, the University of Bosowa and the University of Science Malaysia, also contribute, but less frequently.

Through the diversification of institutions, a collaborative research landscape is emerging, with institutions from different regions (including the USA, Indonesia and Jordan) potentially involved in collaborations.

Table 5. Main author affiliations (Scopus)

Affiliation	Articles
University Of Bahrain	10
University Of New Orleans	6
University Bosowa	5
Amman University College	2
Canterbury Christ Church University	2
Ims Unison University	2
Institut Agama Islam Darussalam (Iaid) Ciamis	2
Kingdom University	2
Universiti Sains Malaysia	2
Ajloun University College	1

Source: Author

Furthermore, analysis of author affiliations using the WoS database reveals that three institutions dominate contributions: Kazan Federal University, Muhammadiyah Sumatra Utara University and Muhammadiyah Surakarta University, with contributions amounting to 3 articles each, as shown in Table 6. Together with Atatürk University, Multimedia University and Brunei Darussalam University, these institutions seem to occupy a crucial place in the research covered by the selected articles, attesting to their commitment on an international scale. This grouping of institutions suggests that expertise in this field is centralized, and that research collaborations are undoubtedly in place.

However, it should be pointed out that affiliation with an institution does not necessarily guarantee the quality of research. For a more comprehensive assessment, other indicators, such as citations, are essential.

Table 6. Main author affiliations (WoS)

Affiliation	Articles
Kazan Fed Univ	3
Univ Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara	3
Univ Muhammadiyah Surakarta	3
Ataturk Univ	2

Multimedia Univ	2
Univ Brunei Darussalam	2
Kafkas Univ	1
Univ Medan Area	1
Univ Padjadjaran	1
Univ Pembangunan Panca Budi	1

Source: Author

In fact, of the 24 Scopus documents, 10 are characterized by a high number of citations. These articles, published recently (between 2020 and 2023), cover a wide range of topics in the fields of economics, finance and innovation. We observe a certain tendency towards citation concentration, with some articles, such as those by Rabbani MR and Hudaefi FA, receiving more attention than others. The Normalized Citation Score (NCS) shows that Menne F.'s article (2022) has the greatest impact, depending on the year of publication. These contributions highlight recent and influential research in our field, conducted by senior authors and published in a variety of journals. However, the analysis of the most cited papers in the WoS data covers only 6 articles. Due to the low number of citations (maximum 3) and articles, it is not yet possible to identify dominant authors or topics.

Table 7. Most cited documents worldwide (Scopus)

Paper	DOI	Total Citations	TC per year	TC normalized
RABBANI MR, 2020, INT J ECON BUS ADM	10.35808/ijeba/444	73	14,60	2,34
RABBANI MR, 2021, J OPEN INNOV: TECHNOL MARK COMPLEX	10.3390/joitmc7020136	69	17,25	3,21
HUDAEFI FA, 2020, QUAL RES FINANC MARKETS	10.1108/QRFM-05-2019-0058	47	9,40	1,50
MENNE F, 2022, J OPEN INNOV: TECHNOL MARK COMPLEX	10.3390/joitmc8010018	39	13,00	4,78
ALSHATER MM, 2022, HELIYON	10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10385	27	9,00	3,31
QUDAH H, 2023, INTERN J FINANCIAL STUD	10.3390/ijfs11020076	11	5,50	2,00

HUDAEFI FA, 2023, QUAL RES FINANC MARKETS	10.1108/QRFM-04-2022-0058	8	4,00	1,45
RAZAK MIA, 2021, PERTANIKA J SOC SCI HUMANIT	10.47836/PJSSH.28.4.40	8	2,00	0,37
GLAVINA S, 2021, J RISK FINANC MANAG	10.3390/jrfm14120602	8	2,00	0,37
FIRDAUS TM, 2022, INT CONF CYBER IT SERV MANAG, CITSM	10.1109/CITSM56380.2022.9935926	7	2,33	0,86

Source: Author

The thematic network also highlights the broader context of Islamic Fintech, represented by nodes of different colors. The results show the existence of several clusters illustrated in Figure 4 that testify to the close links between Fintech and Islamic finance that are at the heart of the network, linked to different aspects of the industry that join the same color, namely Industry 4.0, Shariah compliance, Islamic crowdfunding, innovation, artificial intelligence, among others. These concepts are key to understanding how Islamic Fintech works and its impact on sustainable development, while also highlighting its integration into the global financial landscape. These nodes are in turn linked to a series of concepts such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), income stability, micro-entrepreneurs, Islamic banking, e-commerce and data analytics. And on the other, to the COVID-19 pandemic, post COVID-19, open innovation, organizational sustainability and Generation Z. This diversity underlines the ability of Islamic Fintech to respond to a variety of global challenges.

Figure 3. Thematic network analysis (Scopus)

Source: Author

3.2.2. Discussion

Raza Rabbani et al. (2021) state in their article that Islamic finance is sustainable because it provides ethical financial services, shares risks equitably and is subject to good governance. It promotes asset-backed financing, ensures financial and social stability, encourages financial inclusion and contributes to the inclusive development of society, which is important for sustainable development. Unlike traditional financial approaches, it calls for an equitable distribution of wealth and promotes social justice by providing social financing tools such as Qard, Zakat and Waqf.

Islamic finance therefore presents itself as an attractive alternative financial model focused on sustainability, equity and social responsibility, offering a sustainable alternative to traditional financial systems, reinforced by Fintech in the current context.

Islamic Fintech combines the principles of Islamic finance with innovative financial technologies. It has the potential to revolutionize the Islamic financial sector to make it more accessible, inclusive and efficient (Rabbani et al., 2022), by offering innovative financial services, improving transparency and lowering costs (Mujiatun et al., 2022). Tarique & Ahmed (2021) emphasize that future research should focus on the consequences of this practice on financial inclusion, economic growth and sustainable development. This satisfied us, as it was our main concern in our present study.

The latter examined a total of 30 documents, 24 of which came from Scopus, including 10 articles, representing 41.7% of the total. In addition, it includes 7 book chapters, 4 conference papers and 3 journals. In addition, 6 documents from WoS are also reviewed, including 4 articles, one journal and one conference paper.

The articles reviewed present different methodological approaches, ranging from conceptual studies to quantitative and bibliometric analyses. Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi (2022), for example, developed a conceptual model of Islamic crowdfunding to finance SMEs, but did not include empirical data, which limited their assessment of actual impact. In contrast, studies such as Menne et al. (2022) used quantitative methodologies, such as structural equation modeling (SEM), to analyze the impact of Islamic Fintech on the viability of SMEs in Indonesia. For their part, Dawood et al. (2022) combined bibliometric analysis, systematic literature review and meta-analysis to explore trends and challenges in the Islamic Fintech sector, identifying lack of regulation and low technology adoption as major obstacles.

The authors have tackled different issues, but several recurring themes emerge. A common thread is the issue of financial inclusion, particularly in rural areas or for populations excluded from traditional financial systems. Thus, articles by Allaymoun & Hag Hamid (2020) focus on the integration of mobile technologies to facilitate access to Salam financing in agriculture, while Hassan, Bashar, et al. (2022) emphasize the potential of Islamic Fintech to include Muslim populations excluded from the conventional banking system. In addition, studies of participatory finance models (such as P2P lending) highlight the challenges associated with regulation and technology adoption in specific contexts such as Indonesia (Firdaus et al., 2022). Blockchain technologies and their potential to improve the transparency and efficiency of Islamic financial services represent another major issue.

Although some results have not been thoroughly evaluated empirically, overall they are promising. The study by Menne et al. (2022) found that Islamic fintech has a limited direct effect on the financial performance of SMEs, but makes a strong contribution to their long-term viability, alongside human capital development and business diversification. Hassan, Bashar, et al. (2022) argue that Islamic fintech services, in particular crowdfunding, are powerful levers for supporting SMEs and economic growth (SDG 8). Alshater et al. (2022) also found that Islamic fintech, in particular crowdfunding, is a key instrument for achieving financial inclusion and supporting SMEs. Drawing on the terms of impact on the SDGs, the research reveals significant potential for promoting the reduction of inequality (SDG 10) and inclusive economic growth (SDG 8), with the aim also of identifying avenues for better integration of ESG criteria into Islamic fintech practices. However, these results remain limited due to the challenges posed by horizontal business models, such as the use of artificial intelligence and Big Data, which require more in-depth study.

The main opportunities for Islamic Fintech that emerge from the selected articles thus include increasing financial inclusion by offering Islamic financial services to unbanked populations (Hudaefi et al., 2023), developing new and innovative Islamic financial products and services (Dawood et al., 2022), reducing the costs and increasing the efficiency of Islamic financial transactions (Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi, 2022), stimulating economic growth by supporting SMEs and entrepreneurs (Hudaefi et al., 2023). And, of course, contributing to sustainable development by financing green and social projects (Hudaefi, 2020).

Collaboration between Fintech and Islamic finance players has proved essential. By fostering innovation and developing new financial solutions, these partnerships can contribute to the sustainable development of Islamic finance and its positive effects on society (CengiZ & Özkan, 2023; Yuspin & Fauzie, 2023). Indeed, it makes it possible to offer more affordable and convenient financial services to a wide range of customers, thus promoting financial inclusion. In addition, it improves the efficiency and transparency of financial transactions, strengthening customer confidence and the integrity of the Islamic financial system (Firmansyah & Harsanto, 2022).

Clearly, Islamic Fintech offers many opportunities, but they also pose many challenges, most notably a lack of public awareness and understanding of Islamic Fintech (Glavina et al., 2021), insufficient and unclear regulations in some countries (Dawood et al., 2022), a shortage of skills and expertise in the field (Glavina et al., 2021), cybersecurity and data protection risks (Firdaus et al., 2022), as well as the high cost of these technologies (Glavina et al., 2021). The authors advocate raising public awareness of Islamic Fintech and its benefits.

Islamic participatory financing

According to the study by Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi (2022), Islamic participatory financing can address the lack of SME financing in Islamic countries, promoting financial inclusion and fostering economic sustainability. However, certain regulatory adjustments are required to ensure the long-term viability of this model.

Mobile applications

The mobile application e-Salam , studied by Allaymoun & Hag Hamid (2020), shows how Islamic Fintech is being used to support specific sectors such as agriculture. While it promotes financial inclusion, its uptake remains limited in rural areas, hampering its potential impact on reducing inequalities (SDG 10)

Research into Islamic Fintech

A bibliometric analysis by Alshater et al. (2022) highlighted the strong correlation between Islamic Fintech and financial inclusion. Nevertheless, regulation and financial education remain obstacles to its widespread adoption. For Islamic Fintech to contribute fully to economic growth and the reduction of inequality, these obstacles must be overcome.

Crowdfunding and blockchain

The study by Dawood et al. (2022) reveals that the integration of blockchain into Islamic crowdfunding has the potential to enhance the transparency and efficiency of sustainable financing. But also these models still face challenges relating to regulation and validation of their long-term impact.

P2P lending

According to the study by Firdaus et al. (2022) on P2P lending, it has considerable potential to improve financial inclusion, particularly in marginalized economic sectors. However, regulatory changes are essential to ensure widespread adoption and lasting impact.

Green projects

Rabbani (2022) highlights the role of Fintech in sustainable development through the facilitation of green projects via tools such as participatory finance, AI for personalized portfolios and blockchain for green bonds. Initiatives such as Ant Forest, where eco-responsible behavior is rewarded by the planting of real trees, testify to the impact of these innovations. Yet challenges remain, particularly in terms of regulation and long-term impact assessment. Fintech therefore appears to be an essential lever in the democratization and acceleration of sustainable financing.

Success factors for Islamic Fintech

Qualitative analysis by Firmansyah & Harsanto (2022) shows that the success of an Islamic Fintech relies on several key elements: collaboration between the parties involved, clear regulation and effective service management. To create a sustainable and responsible ecosystem, in line with SDGs 1, 8 and 9, it is essential that these factors are taken into account.

Islamic Fintech thus has great potential to support sustainable development and financial inclusion. Models such as crowdfunding , P2P lending and blockchain are helping to reduce economic inequalities and improve access to finance for the unbanked. However, a number of challenges remain, mainly related to regulatory barriers, the lack of financial literature and the need for a stable legal framework to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of these technologies (Razak et al., 2020). Further research is therefore needed to further assess the practical impact of these models.

4. CONCLUSION

Islamic Fintech is still in its infancy and trying to keep up with the rapid development it is witnessing worldwide. Indeed, publications are concentrated in a few countries and written by a small number of authors, indicating that research into Islamic Fintech is still limited and that there is a need to make a contribution in this area. This systematic review therefore took a close look at the literature, gathering articles from the Scopus and Web of Science databases.

It offers a perspective that builds on previous research and opens up new avenues of research focused on the sustainability, financial inclusion and long-term viability of Islamic finance in Fintech, while highlighting its continued relevance.

However, this research has its limitations, as it is based on only two databases, demonstrating the need for further studies using other databases. Furthermore, to validate the findings and better understand Islamic Fintech's contribution to sustainable development, other qualitative methods, such as expert interviews, could be adopted.

Furthermore, Islamic banks in Morocco in particular need to realize that Fintech is here to stay, and that Shariah-compliant Fintech services offer them an opportunity to improve the sustainability of the financial system, which requires rapidly integrating innovative Fintech-based services to compete with the traditional financial system. To take full advantage of these opportunities, several measures can be considered.

The Moroccan government should foster an innovation-friendly regulatory framework, through investment-friendly policies and incentives, and engage in research and development to catalyze the emergence of sustainable, Shariah-compliant financial solutions, launch training and awareness-raising initiatives to enhance the qualifications of financial sector personnel and communicate the benefits of Islamic Fintech to the general public, and finally encourage support for startups and Islamic Fintech projects geared towards sustainable development, notably through public-private partnerships and incubation programs.

By adopting these measures, Morocco can not only catch up in the Islamic Fintech space, but also become a leader in sustainable financial innovation in the region.

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